

Table 1. Health-information topics in three time-windows.

Category	Sub-category	No. of papers
2007-2011		
A. Health information behavior	A1. Minority issues	67
	A2. Research method-qualitative	59
2012-2016		
B. Health Behavior (research methodology)	B1. Research method-qualitative	425
	B2. Specific disease	29
	B3. Information behavior (need, search), social media as platform, highlight the attributes in various regions/countries	35
2017-2021		
C1. Health librarianship (Library role in health information literacy)		131
C2. Health information analysis (application of health information technologies: health records, text mining for subject analysis)		49

Evolutions in Health-Information Topics

The second GN algorithm analysis was applied to cluster the topics of the articles in two consecutive time-windows based on their cosine similarity of the weighted keyword vectors. Those topics in two consecutive time-windows were clustered together, and their cosine similarity greater than 0.5 were considered to belong to the same topic flows, and the evolution of research is represented in Figure 2, which shown as Sankey flow (Riehmman et al., 2005). The results show that the two research topics, health information behaviour and research strategies remained attracting research interests and social media as an information source or platform for information exchange form the third research track. Those three tracks from the second period were vanished and the two new topics, health librarianship and use of technologies for information process, drew more research attention in the third period.

Note. Newly: newly developed topic, not traced from the previous time-window; Grown: topic extended to the next time-window; Ceased: continued topic from the previous time-window, but no following trace; Declined: short-term developed topic.

Figure 2. Sankey flow of health-information topics evolution.

Conclusions

This study adopted GN algorithm analysis and Sankey flow to reveal the research topics related to health information services and the shift of the research interests over the last 15 years, from 2007 to 2021. Health information service is a unique

research area in library and information science studies. The results show a continuous concern on the related issues, as well as transformation of the research attributes and an emerging research theme, health librarianship including related information behaviour study, health information literacy, service design and common recognised research strategies, was established.

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